

Overview of Zenodo repository associated with the publication "Modulational instability in large-amplitude linear laser wakefields", A. von Boetticher, R. Walczak, S. M. Hooker, Physical Review E, 2022.

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namelist.py:

Contains initialisation parameters for the particle-in-cell code SMILEI, used to perform numerical calculations to generate data for Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 4 in the main paper, and Fig. 1 in the Supplementary Material.

Simulations were performed using SMILEI v.4.1 and Python version 2.7.6.

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run.pbs:

Contains configuration parameters for the Cray XC30 high-performance computing system ARCHER.